

Real time variable rate spraying based on 3D visual inputs

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Summary

Plant protection product (PPP) savings up to 25 % in the specialty crops sector have been demonstrated by smart spraying technology like the Smartomizer H3O (Berger *et al.*, 2019; Berger *et al.*, 2022). Nevertheless, the Farm-to-Fork strategy within the EU's Green Deal has set the objective of 50 % hazardous pesticides reduction by 2030.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) combined with high-end *variable rate application (VRA)* spraying technology is key to address growers' pressing environmental and productive challenges. Fede's AIs system (the growers' "eyes on the ground") is a comprehensive agronomic solution based on computer vision and AI edge processing that allows to see crops/canopy with 3D stereo cameras. In the sequel, these visual inputs, with a well-balanced degree of detail and temporal resolution, provide information on crop dimensions, which facilitate real time VRA sprayer adjustments following the philosophy "See & Save".

The following presents AIs enabled VRA spraying field trial results, which demonstrate that the latest advances in specialty crops sprayer developments allow to save an additional 28% and 36% of PPP over a high-end baseline sprayer in the investigated almond and orange cases, respectively.

Key words: 3D Computer Vision, Spot Spraying, Variable Rate Application, VRA, pesticide use reduction, drift reduction, *Smartomizer*, EU LIFE Programme

Introduction

According to the *World Health Organization (WHO)*, low fruit and vegetable intake causes approximately 1.7 million deaths per year (WHO, 2019). At the same time, studies predict serious fruit shortages up to 2050, with the world population reaching 9 billion (FAO, 2009 and Grethe *et al.*, 2011), while pests and diseases are responsible for 25% to 40% yield loss before harvest globally (FAO, 2020). Moreover, pesticide residues are the most important food-related concern for EU citizens (EUROB, 2010), and the *European Food Safety Authority (EFSA)*, announced that more than 45 % of food products analysed (apples, head cabbage, lettuce, peaches, spinach, strawberries, tomatoes, barley, oats, wine grapes, swine fat, and milk) contain pesticide residues (EFSA, 2021).

Thus, reducing the use of pesticides in fruit production is a major global societal challenge and it is in line with European Directive 2009/128/EC, demanding *Integrated Pest Management (IPM)* as well as with 2016/2031/EC, which requires that a proportionate and effective response to plant health threats is established through a combination of technological,

ecological and institutional management. Still, large parts of conventional spraying equipment are still highly inefficient. The size of the problem has been quantified in the 3-year study ‘Save Spray’, directed by the *Valencian Institute of Agriculture Research* (IVIA), in collaboration with FEDE, the University of Lleida, and the *Polytechnical University of Catalonia* (UPC) (Moltó *et al.*, 2012). The study revealed that 50 % of *plant protection product* (PPP) do not reach the plants but are lost due to drift, run-off, and ground losses when using conventional spraying equipment. As a result, a large number of pesticides are found in ambient air (Coscollà *et al.*, 2013) contaminating the environment, with considerable negative effects for biodiversity, bee life, bystanders, and the ecosystem as a whole. Addressing this serious environmental problem, the EU Life-F₃ project demonstrated, in the case of the Spanish vineyard *Viñas del Vero* (VERO) and the Portuguese olive plantation *OUTEIRO Do Outeiro Sociedade Agricola, S.A.* (OUTEIRO), that reduction of over 25 % of biocidal products and/or pesticides is possible simply through the correct use of existing high-end spraying equipment (Berger *et al.*, 2022).

The presented work takes the developments one step further by equipping the high-end spraying equipment with the capability to individually switch all nozzles based on input commands from a 3D stereo vision system with *artificial intelligence edge processing capabilities* (AIs), which can be considered as the growers' "eyes on the ground". The algorithms inside, with a well-balanced degree of detail and temporal resolution, provide information on crop dimensions, which facilitate real time variable rate sprayer adjustments for high precision PPP spraying and foliar fertilization.

Materials and Methods

AIs Sprayer Technology

The AIs system, as indicated in Fig. 1, is fitted on a tractor, and contains two stereo vision cameras per side. Mounting AIs on the tractor enables sprayer-independent crop statistics collection. However, collecting data with AIs also bears significant technical challenges, *e.g.* the timing for spray nozzle actuation is dependent on information captured from another vehicle, with sprayer and tractor only loosely coupled. Furthermore, establishing a reliable high-speed data connection between vehicles that get frequently disconnected and reconnected under harsh conditions is a challenge. AIs here provides a robust Ethernet solution. Moreover, the issue of keeping camera lenses clean is addressed with a pressurised air-curtain system that shields off the lenses from dust, rain, *etc.* Pressurised air is also used to cool cameras and the AIs' edge processing unit.

The data collected can be directly used to act on the sprayer, *e.g.* to open and close spray nozzles as a function of detected tree dimensions and density. To do so, sprayers have to be “AIs-enabled”, which means, they need an Ethernet connection into the *Sprayer Control System* (SCS) over which to receive proprietary AIs commands, and they must be fitted with actuators, *i.e.* the *Nozzle Control Unit* (NCU), to open and close nozzles individually, while maintaining spray pressure constant.

Fig. 1. Fede's AIs system connected to an AIs-enabled sprayer in almond field.

Looking at Fig. 2, it becomes apparent that Life-AIs material is much more than a sprayer. It is a whole speciality crops agricultural management environment bringing digitalization and precision to 3D crops. Sprayers with a Fede developed *Sprayer Control System (SCS)* on the implement side connect via Wi-Fi with a *Terminal Application in the tractor's cabin (TAPP)*.

Fig. 2. Fede's AIs system embedded into the Specialty Crops Platform (SCP).

The tractor carries a *speciality crops gateway (SCG)* that guides the sprayer operator and connects tractor and sprayer via cellular modem to the Internet and from there to FEDE's Cloud, referred to as *Specialty Crops Platform (SCP)*. Farmers and agronomic advisors have

access to the Speciality Crops Platform *via* web *graphical user interfaces* (GUIs). This way, they can perform actions like sending prescriptions, or work orders to the sprayer operator, or monitoring and documenting results. Moreover, through a GUI, back-office staff can post-process data. For example, it can automatically produce the farm book that records all plant protection product treatments. Moreover, interoperability with third party service providers is assured through *Application Programming Interfaces* (APIs), collectively referred to as *Specialty Crop Integration Centre* (SCIC).

AIs and Baseline Reference Set-up

The baseline sprayer is a Smartomizer H₃O of 2000 l, with $n = 26$ identical individual switchable nozzles, $n/2$ per side. Test results are obtained in traditional orange and almond groves with the spraying situations as outlined in Fig. 3. Fig. 3. (a) shows the baseline situation, where the sprayer is configured manually in a conventional way selecting the baseline spray volume Q (l ha⁻¹) with respect to the Tree Row Volume (Świechowski *et al.*, 2012), *i.e.*

$$Q = (H \cdot W \cdot k \cdot 10\,000) / R \quad (\text{equ. 1}),$$

where H is the tree height excluding the bare trunk (m), W is the tree width (m), R is the interrow distance (m), and k is the unit volume (l m⁻³).

The flow rate per nozzle q is then calculated as in (Świechowski *et al.*, 2012), *i.e.*

$$q = (Q \cdot R \cdot v) / (600 \cdot n) \quad (\text{equ. 2}),$$

where additionally v is the driving velocity in km h⁻¹.

Fig. 3. Spraying situation. (a) baseline without AIs. (b) with AIs scanning of tree dimensions.

In Fig 3 (b) the sprayer receives input from the AIs system with instructions to switch individual nozzles on and off for segments of the canopy where no or only very little foliar mass is detected.

Nozzle opening and closing times and therewith the flow through the nozzles is logged for post processing data analysis. To assure no negative impact of the AIs system on distribution and deposition, hydro sensible paper is distributed over the canopy, putting especial emphasis on areas close to canopy holes where AIs is expected to switch nozzles.

The Orange and Almond Test Fields

Trials are performed in an almond and an orange plantation in the Valencia (Spain) area, with field satellite map as well as individual tree views as given in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Satellite, RGB, and depth view of (a) almond and (b) orange test field/tree.

In the lower part of Fig. 4., comparing the RGB (Red, Green, Blue) image to the left and the depth image to the right one gets a notion for which kind of information the 3D cameras are gathering. In fact, all the grey shadings, correspond to different depths that are then converted by AIs' processing algorithms into actionable nozzle opening and closing commands.

Results

PPP Savings due to AIs

In the almond case the target spray volume Q_{target} is 800 l ha^{-1} , while in the orange case with much denser foliar coverage the target spray volume Q_{target} is 2500 l ha^{-1} . Monitoring of spray parameter of the baseline shows that the sprayer regulates spraying processes so that the actual applied spray volume $Q_{applied}$ stays in both cases within $\pm 2.5 \%$ of the target.

For the AIs situation, the notion of treatment “*equivalent to*” was devised, based on the fact that many growers are used to define a constant rate target spray volume. However, when AIs autonomously closes nozzles, while maintaining the spray pressure constant, the sprayer

applies over the whole area a quantity that results in spray coverage “equivalent to” having ordered a uniform treatment with Q_{target} , but where due to AIs induces savings the actual applied spray volume stays below, *i.e.* $Q_{applied} \leq Q_{target}$. To express that AIs enabled sprayers intentionally stay most of the time below the uniform spray volume, Q_{target} is renamed into “ $Q_{equivalent}$ ”, and AIs induces spray volume savings are, hence, expressed as:

$$S_{AIs} = Q_{equivalent} - Q_{applied} \quad (\text{equ. 3}).$$

To ensure that the VRA treatment is “equivalent to” the uniform baseline treatment, it is of utmost importance that the spray efficacy is not diminishing. Although spray efficacy trials were not feasible due to time constraints in the presented work, a visual inspection of hydro-sensible paper distributed in the canopy was conducted for the baseline case (a) and AIs case (b), which showed comparable spray distribution and deposition.

To get a feeling for the nozzle opening and closing process, Fig. 5. shows the number of opened nozzles over time for the almond case.

Fig. 5. Time series of nozzle opening in almond case.

With the baseline sprayer manually adjusted by a spray technician to a mid-size tree, it can be seen that, it operates with seven constantly open nozzles per side. On the other hand, the AIs enabled sprayer dynamically regulates this number of nozzles, reaching a maximum value of 10 nozzles open per side. That the AIs algorithm can open more nozzles means that AIs also adjust to trees that are higher than the mid-size tree with the intention to achieve ideal coverage even of these trees bigger than the norm, that in the baseline case have the risk of being slightly under-sprayed.

Clearly, if more nozzles can be opened by the AIs sprayer than in the baseline case, one could end up in a situation where more spray volume is applied with AIs. However, in canopies with sufficient amounts of irregularities and gaps, as it is the case for the selected orange and almond filed, the savings outweigh, leading to the applied spray volumes as displayed in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. Spray volume as applied in baseline and AIs case in almond and orange field.

Fig. 6 shows that AIs induced spray volume saving is S_{AIs} 285 L and 704 L in the almond and orange field, respectively, which relates to saving percentages of 36 % and 28 %. This is a clear indication that with AIs additional savings can be obtained in comparison to a high-end well-adjusted constant rate sprayer.

Discussion

For our all health and wellbeing, pesticide use in crop production needs to be reduced and we are here in line with EU policies like the Green Deal and the Farm-to-Fork strategy. Lots can already be gained in following the “Calibration of Orchard Sprayers” procedures as in (Świechowski *et al.*, 2012), and trials in the predecessor Life-F3 project revealed savings of up to 25 % just through manually well-adjusted spraying equipment.

The work here goes a step further and demonstrates additional savings of 28% to 36% over a well-adjusted constant rate sprayer due to AIs induced variable rate application. While AIs works well in the particular contexts of the almond and orange field, it should be noted that the effectively achievable savings depend on the variability of the canopy. In very heterogeneous canopies with little holes, less savings will be achievable, while in highly variable canopies with holes or even entire trees missing, savings can be very significant.

All in all, these results indicate that the latest advances in 3D computer vision enabled Specialty Crops sprayer developments allow growers to significantly reduce their production costs due to PPP inputs savings in line with EU objectives.

In the future, the AIs system will also stimulate savings of fertilizers, water and *Greenhouse Gasses* (GHGs), with related demonstration activities already ongoing in the framework of the EU co-funded project *Life-AIs* aligned with the moto “*Life-AIs: See & Save!*”.

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